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[Design, modelling and errors measurement of wheeled mobile robots](#)

Abstract: This paper presents the mechanical design process of an omni-directional mobile robot. In addition, the kinematics equations of the final design are derived, and the inverse Jacobian matrix of the robot is presented. The dynamic equations of motion for the final design are derived in a symbolic form, assuming that no slip occurs on the wheel in the spin direction. In order to validate the kinematics and dynamic equation, we carried out consequences of simulation using two pieces of software, Maple and Working Model. Finally, the mobile robot is moved in given trajectories and the systematic errors of the robot are determined. To overcome the problems, a new method was introduced in which the robot was programmed to move in the direction of each wheel shaft.

Keywords: Differential drive, Modelling, Odometry test, Omni-directional, Robot, Simulation, Systematic error.

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